

Deliverable D-JRP19-WP3.4
REPORT ON THE GENETIC
POPULATION STRUCTURE
OF *C. PARVUM* AND *G.*
DUODENALIS

Workpackage 3 of
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE

Responsible Partners: P27-ISS, P11-
RKI, P41-SVA, P23-UoS

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP19-23
Project Acronym	PARADISE
Author	Simone M. Cacciò (ISS), Karin Troell (SVA), Martha Betson (UoS), Christian Klotz (RKI)
Other contributors	PARADISE Consortium
Due month of the report	54
Actual submission month	59
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, Save date: 2 November 2022
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.4

REPORT ON THE GENETIC POPULATION STRUCTURE OF *C. PARVUM* AND *G. DUODENALIS*

**This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – PARAsite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation**

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>)

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE–WP3 Design, implementation and validation of MLST schemes

Task:

**JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP3-T3 Development of SOPs for the *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*
MLST schemes**

Project Leader: Simone M. Cacciò, ISS; Deputy Project Leader: Karin Troell, SVA

WP Leader: Karin Troell, SVA; Deputy WP Leader: Christian Klotz, RKI

Contacts: Simone M. Cacciò, simone.caccio@iss.it

Karin Troell, karin.troell@sva.se

Christian Klotz, klotz@rki.de

1. Background

The PARADISE project aims to deliver informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for the food-borne parasites *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Using genomics and metagenomics, the project is generating much needed data to enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis for development and testing of improved strain-typing schemes. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices are under development and validation. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches to control *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in the European food chain. Within WP3, the objectives of the project were 1) to select new markers *in silico* for robust high resolution genotyping of *C. parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*; 2) to develop multilocus sequence typing (MLST) schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*; and 3) to conduct an inter-laboratory comparison of MLST schemes.

This report deals with interpretation of the genetic data generated in WP3 in terms of the population structure of *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* in Europe.

2. Report on the genetic population structure of *C. parvum*

2.1 Introduction

Cryptosporidium parvum is the most important zoonotic species in the genus *Cryptosporidium*. It causes gastrointestinal disease in humans and other animals, particularly young ruminants, and has a global distribution. Infection is transmitted by direct faecal-oral contact or by ingestion of water and food contaminated with parasite oocysts. Due to the lack of morphological differences among oocysts, molecular biology techniques are used to distinguish isolates, support epidemiological investigations and understand transmission pathways. To date, most studies have relied upon sequence analysis of the highly polymorphic glycoprotein 60 (*gp60*) gene, yet analysis of a single gene cannot be used as a reliable proxy for the genetic identity of an isolate or to infer the genetic structure of populations of parasites. Within WP3, the project has generated many new Whole Genome Sequence (WGS) and used this information to identify novel polymorphic gene markers to develop a new Multi-Locus Sequence Typing (MLST) scheme. This scheme is based on eight markers, each located on one of the eight *C. parvum* chromosomes.

2.2 Results

The MLST scheme has been applied to a large collection of 337 parasite isolates collected across Europe, including 113 human isolates and 224 animal isolates, namely 202 from cattle, 15 from sheep and seven from goats (Appendix 1). This effort generated 2696 sequences (337 for each of the eight markers), with identification of 127 different MLSTs.

Figure 1.. Miminum Spanning Tree showing relationships among MLST types. Isolates from different countries are coded with different colours.

Figure 2. Minimum Spanning Tree showing relationships among MLST types. The different parasite's hosts are represented with different colours.

3. Report on the genetic population structure of *G. duodenalis*

3.1 Introduction

Giardia duodenalis is a species complex that comprises eight genetically very different groups (referred to as assemblages A to H). Human disease is mainly caused by potentially zoonotic assemblages A and B. Like for *C. parvum*, morphological differences among *Giardia* cysts cannot be used to distinguish isolates and molecular biology techniques are needed. One needs also consider that the genome of *Giardia* is tetraploid (16n in the cysts) and that different grades of allelic sequence heterozygosity (ASH) exist. In assemblage B (~ 0.5%), ASH is typically greater than in assemblage A (typically < 0,05%). Therefore, different strategies for molecular typing of assemblage A and B are required. For assemblage A, a recently published typing procedure, based on 6 newly defined markers showing no or very modest level of ASH, has been applied to evaluate its discriminatory power. For assemblage B, the project has generated new Whole Genome Sequence (WGS) data, and used this information to identify novel polymorphic gene markers to develop a new MLST scheme. This scheme is based on seven markers, distributed over the five *G. duodenalis* chromosomes.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 *G. duodenalis* assemblage A

A collection of 60 human-derived and 11 animal-derived isolates, collected in Europe and on other continents, was genotyped at the six markers, with identification of five novel variants at five of the six markers. After inclusion of previously published genotyping data and exclusion of isolates whose sequences showed allelic sequence heterozygosity (ASH), a dataset of 146 isolates was analysed. Analyses of the typing data showed the presence of 78 distinct MLST types. Phylogenetic analysis confirmed that sub-assemblage All only comprises human-derived isolates, whereas sub-assemblage AI comprises all animal-derived isolates and a few human-derived isolates, suggesting limited zoonotic transmission (Figure 1). Within sub-assemblage All, isolates from two outbreaks, which occurred in Sweden and Italy, had unique and distinct MLST types. Population genetic analysis showed a lack of clustering by geographical origin of the isolates (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Minimum Spanning Tree showing relationships between the different MLST types. The geographical origin of the isolates is indicated with colours. The number inside each circle indicated the MLST type, from 1 to 78.

3.2.2 *G. duodenalis* assemblage B

The MLST scheme has been applied to a collection of parasite isolates collected across Europe, including 80 human isolates and two animal isolates. The presence of ASH as a hallmark of assemblage B isolates has been confirmed by the analysis. Altogether, 66 isolates showed ASH that varies between 4-105 bp within the 3897 bp of the concatenated MLST sequences (i.e., affecting 0.1-2.7% of nucleotide positions). Notably, 16 isolates showed no ASH.

Sequences with ASH are not suitable for analysis using phylogenetic tools. Therefore, sequences were aligned and clustered for similarity according to the Clustal Omega algorithm, and represented as a heat map showing the number of different single nucleotide positions between isolates (Fig. 3). This analysis showed a separation of the population into two clusters. Cluster 1 represents isolates with sequences with no or low ASH. Both animal isolates are found in this group. Interestingly, the sequence of the cat isolate from Sweden was identical to that of an unrelated human patient isolate from Germany. Cluster 2 represents isolates with ASH. Strikingly, the isolates of a documented assemblage B outbreak in Italy are found in cluster 2, but clearly form a sub-cluster with significantly lower SNP variation between outbreak isolates compared to non-outbreak isolates.

Figure 3. Heatmap of single nucleotide variation between *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B isolates. Population structure of assemblage B shows two clusters separating isolates with no or low ASH content (cluster 1) from isolates with high ASH content (cluster 2). Isolates from an Italian *G. duodenalis* outbreak form a sub-cluster within cluster 2.

4. Conclusions

The availability of new polymorphic markers for both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* was exploited to generate typing data at the European level. Interpretation of these typing data showed that the population structure of *C. parvum* is complex, with no clear clustering on the basis of host and only partial clustering by geographic origin (i.e., country) of the isolates. Work is in progress to compare the MLST data with results from another typing scheme based on Variable Number of Tandem Repeats (VNTR), in terms of discriminatory power but also from the perspective of the inferred population structure.

In the case of *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage A, we confirm the presence of two subpopulations, one (AI) comprising all animal isolates and a few human isolates, while the second (AII) comprises only

human isolates. This suggests that zoonotic transmission is uncommon. Based on the available data, the population structure does not seem to be influenced by the geographic origin of the isolates.

Finally, we observed that the *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B isolates cluster in two sequence groups comprising isolates with or without ASH in the marker gene sequences, respectively. Importantly, this suggests the existence of two clearly separable sub-populations and shows that parameters to decide on relatedness of isolates based on sequence differences will have to vary depending on subpopulation assignment.

Appendix 1. List of the *C. parvum* isolates used to infer the population structure. The geographical origin and parasite host are indicated.

Country	Human isolates (n)	Cattle isolates (n)	Sheep isolates (n)	Goat isolates (n)
Czechia	-	6	-	-
Denmark	20	30	-	-
Finland	7	10	-	-
France	-	16	3	2
Germany	11	16	-	-
Hungary	-	11	-	-
Italy	-	12	10	5
Netherlands	19	-	-	-
Norway	-	4	-	-
Poland	-	16	-	-
Portugal	-	12	-	-
Slovenia	6	-	-	-
Spain	1	-	-	-
Sweden	7	55	-	-
UK	42	11	2	-
USA	-	3	-	-
Total	113	202	15	7